

Jignyasa - AI powered Intelligent Tutoring System

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Abstract—Recently, there has been surge in integration of artificial intelligence into education to support personalized and learner centered learning experiences. This paper presents design, implementation and functional evaluation of Jignyasa - an AI powered ITS which combines affective computing, constructivist learning theory and adaptive learning using generative AI. The Intelligent Tutoring System is targeted for adult learners who can provide their learning goals, follow personalized learning paths, receive personalized feedback and interact freely with AI one-on-one tutor in a private and supportive environment. It emphasizes emotion awareness, enabling real time responsive tutoring based on learners emotions, engagement while still ensuring privacy.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Education has always been a cornerstone of human development which has enabled societies to evolve and improve quality of life. Traditional classrooms have provided the access to education through structures, face-to-face learning environments. However, they are characterized by rigid curriculum, fixed pacing, and generic approach to teaching. With low teacher-student ratio, each and every student does not get the expected support to grow and learn. The "one-size-fits-all" approach overlooks the learners needs, individual goals and learning styles. The COVID 19 pandemic accelerated the shift from traditional classrooms to online learning environments. Due to restrictions on physical interactions, digital Learning Management systems like Udemy, Udacity, Coursera ensured continuity of access to education. Furthermore, it offered flexibility in time and location. However, these platforms still followed the linear, static learning paths and have struggled to incorporate individual learning preferences. This highlights the need for and intelligent and personalized education solution which will respond to learner's goals, learning styles and cognitive states. A shift from teacher centric systems to learner centric model is a must. Artificial intelligence provides a promising direction in this regard, offering potential to personalize content, pace and feedback in real time.

Limitations of current learning management systems

1. Lack of Personalization: Existing learning management platforms follow a static learning path for all students. Though some systems allow teachers to adjust content manually, it is not possible to scale in asynchronous and remote settings which makes it harder to provide personalized feedback.
2. Teacher-Centric Design: Current learning management platforms still emphasize on content delivery from teachers over learner-driven exploration. This shows a lack of learner-centered education.
3. Absence of Emotional Intelligence: Emotions are core to learning, but most learning management platforms do not incorporate learner's emotional state into the learning experience, which can lead to disengagement.
4. Limited Support for Constructivist Learning: The ability of learners to build knowledge through interaction, self-reflection, and real-world context is often ignored.

1.2 Literature review

1. (Lim, (2020)) states that one-size-fits-all approach is not effective for students as they proceed in diverse learning paths and paces. They proposed Self Evolving Adaptive learning systems for personalized learning.
2. Affective Computing (Picard, 1997) introduced the concept of responding to human emotions and designing learning management systems that should adapt to how learners feel during learning sessions. This is done by continuously exchanging emotional information between the learner and the system.
3. Constructivist Learning Theory emphasizes the learner's role in constructing knowledge and not just passively absorbing it. There have been researches where it proves that constructivist principles can lead to deeper engagement and promote learner-centered education
4. (Sarrafzadeh, (2008)) explored the importance of detecting confusion and disengagement of learners which can be used to adapt teaching approaches.
5. (Ahmad) explored how generative AI can help to create personalized learning content and provide real time adaptive tutoring. However, he mentions about the issues of generative AI like biases, hallucinations, and ethical concerns which must be taken care during learning sessions.
6. (Pham, Singh, and Jahnke (2023)) bring attention older adult learners who are life-long learners. Their work on socio-technical pedagogical usability shows that for adults, usability, emotional support, and personalization are

necessities.

1.3 Objectives

This paper explores the question: “How to design and implement an intelligent LMS that dynamically adapts to a learner’s emotional state, goals, learning styles, and feedback while supporting constructivist, self-directed learning for lifelong learners?”

This includes:

1. Designing a scalable LMS architecture to support modular, AI-driven interactions.
2. Enabling real-time content and UI adaptation based on emotional cues and engagement levels.
3. Integrating LLM-based recommendation systems for personalized learning journeys.
4. Providing an intuitive user interface that adapts to diverse learner needs while supporting both structured guidance and open exploration.

1.4 Summary of contribution

This paper proposes and implements: Jignyasa-an AI powered adaptive learning management system for adult learners. It dynamically personalizes learning paths based on learners prior knowledge, learning goals, learning styles and emotional states through out the sessions. It supports self-regulated learning using cutting edge AI and multi-modal learner analytics, grounded in constructivist learning theory and affective feedback loop principles.

Jignyasa is a holistic learner-centered system that not only senses emotional states using multi-modal inputs (facial expression, interaction data) but also integrates:

1. Constructivist learning principles, promoting scaffold tasks, reflection, and active learning.
2. Real-time adaptive content delivery using reinforcement learning based on both affective and cognitive signals.
3. User interface personalization aligned to both learning styles and emotional states.
4. Privacy-first design, including on-device processing, opt-in features, and trans-

parent learner control over data.

5. Dynamic learner modeling that updates in real-time to support differentiated instruction and feedback.

By bridging emotion recognition with established learning theories and learner agency, Jignaysa offers a next-generation platform that prioritizes personalized, ethical, and pedagogically meaningful learning.

2 RELATED WORK

Multiple advances have been made in learning management systems with focus on personalization and better learner engagement.

1. (Rogrigues,(2010)) developed EduTutor which monitored learner behaviors like workshop participation and commitment. Based on the analysis, a personalized feedback was provided based on performance metrics. Though this early ITS ensures importance of personalization but lacks emotional awareness.
2. (Dewan, (2019)) outlines powerful methodologies for emotion detection with distinction across automatic, semi-automatic and manual. But it also highlights the real world environment challenges for real time emotion detection and privacy concerns.
3. (Behera, (2020)) introduced emotional intelligence detection using gesture based disengagement tracking. But the system lacks pedagogically grounded adaptive learning experiences along with emotion detection.
4. (Kolekar, (2019)) proposed rule based adaptive user interface which modifies based on learner interaction. This supports personalization but lacks holistic view of the learner. It is not emotion aware and does not incorporate pedagogical strategies.
5. (Sayed, (2024)) introduced the concept of using Artificial intelligence to attain personalization. They used ML models like KNN, SVM to classify learners based on learning styles from clickstream data. But it still lacks emotion awareness and constructivism principles.

3 SOLUTION

Jignyasa is a modular and scalable emotion aware Intelligent tutoring system, which is designed to provide personalized learning.

3.1 High Level System Architecture

Figure 1—High level diagram

1. The user Interface is the interaction point for learners. It has been created using React for modular structure and re-usability and Context for easier properties sharing. For better user experience and design, tailwind CSS is used. The user interface routes user inputs to server implemented using Express framework, which then uses Express API Gateway to orchestrate calls to various backend services written in Nodejs and typescript.
2. The Auth Service handles login and registration of a user. It is responsible for session management of the user across learning sessions. This is done using JWT token.

Figure 2—Domain and tutor service

3. At the core of the server, there is domain service which creates a unique learning path based on learners goals, learning style, learners pre-knowledge about the goal and provided PDFs. This is achieved by utilizing RAG and LLM, which helps to define the context for the LLM to respond with. The technical framework used in Langchain, which helps in creating local vector database used for semantic similarities among chunks from inputs and documents. The goals and learning paths are stored in SQLITE database to ensure, learner can resume their learning any time.
4. The tutor service acts as the one-on-one tutor for the learner. It teaches each subtopic based on learning style of the learner and provided context. This is also achieved by utilizing RAG and LLM and langchain for orchestration. All the chat histories are stored in SQLITE database, which can later be retrieved for analysis.

Figure 3—Privacy first design

5. The emotion tracker server tracks emotions of the learner through out learning sessions. The React webcam integration helps to take screenshots of the learners during the sessions which are then analyzed for boredom and stored in SQLITE database. For Privacy first design, A settings is provided for the user to explicitly opt in or out of emotion log analysis.
6. The insights of learners interactions, tutor conversations, emotion logs etc are processed by multi modal learner analytics service. It analyzes the data to provide an holistic view of the learner and to accordingly update the future learning sessions.
7. Adaptive Planner service adjusts the content based on learner progress and

Figure 4—Dashboard

emotional states during last subtopic learning session.

8. The Dashboard services provides learners with real time overview of their engagement, retention score, strengths and weaknesses, and personalized feedback from the tutor service.

4 METHODOLOGY

The implementation process followed a structured approach to validate the feasibility and functional correctness of Jignyasa.

1. **Requirements Gathering:** the process began with brief literature review of emotion aware tutoring systems, current learning management systems. This helps to define the core requirements of an affective, emotionally aware and adaptive Intelligent tutoring system specifically for adult learners.
2. **Problem Statement and Gap identification:** Carried out comparative analysis of existing Learning management systems, which provide personalized content, but ignore learner emotions, self-reflection and adaptive feedback loops. They also do not include constructivist principles and follow traditional rigid structure.
3. **Design and Implementation Strategy:** Based on agile development process, the system architecture was designed. It followed microservices architecture for the advantage of modularity, scalability and extensibility. The Frontend was built considering the clarity required and ease of user for adult learners, with privacy based controls for them to consent on analysis of their interaction data.

4. Evaluation approach: Large scale user testing is a part of future scope, but the current system is evaluated in following ways:
 - (a) Functional testing: Every core module - goal setting, learning path creation, tutoring, progress tracking, personalized feedback, emotional feedback etc is rigorously tested to ensure it is working as expected.
 - (b) Self-reflective evaluation: As an adult learner, I tested the platform in realistic learning scenarios. This helped me to identify design gaps, usability issues, privacy design understanding, and emotional and personalized feedback importance.

5 RESULTS

1. Functional Evaluation: Every core component was successfully implemented and validated with rigorous manual testing
 - (a) Authentication: Every new user with unique username could register in the system. If a learner returns back to continue with their learning session, they can login with valid credentials and shown all their existing goals. The negative testing was also done to ensure no unauthorized usage of the system.
 - (b) Goal Setting and Personalized Learning path: The system allowed learners to setup a goal with PDFs acting as context. The system also analyses the current knowledge of the learner about the goal to create a personalized learning path, focusing on the topics learner is unaware of or has less knowledge about. The learning path includes modular division of goal into subtopics into number of days provided by the learner. This ensures reflective thinking of learner on current knowledge and future learning to master their goal.
 - (c) One-on-One Tutoring: For each subtopic, the tutor starts teaching based on learners learning style. The learning style includes learners preferred learning style and adaptive learning style understood from the analysis of previous learning sessions.
 - (d) Emotion aware tracker: the emotions were tracked during learning sessions in regular intervals which were then analyzed to update the teaching strategy in next learning session.
 - (e) Privacy first design: Learners had control over what data they shared - opt in or out of emotion capture. This enables ethical usage of data.
 - (f) Dashboard: After each learning session, the learner was provided with

their personalized feedback from the tutor about their strengths, weaknesses and what should they do in next session. It also told the retention rate, for learner to understand and track their growth. This helped with self-reflection.

2. Alignment with theoretical foundations

- (a) The systems design is inspired by (Picard (2007)) Affective computing, where the emotional data was continuously exchanged between the user and the systems, with learners consent.
- (b) Constructivist approach is incorporated in tutoring sessions to ensure learner driven learning sessions, to let learner actively participate.
- (c) The multi-agent architecture and modular structure supports future integration of better LLMs, other modalities for holistic view of learner, better real time emotional recognition.

3. Self Reflective Evaluation

- (a) Goal Setting and pre-knowledge assessment: These features helped me understand the gaps by identifying current weak subtopics. It helped me understand my learning needs.
- (b) AI tutor conversation: One-on-One tutoring promoted meta cognitive reflection. I found it easier to express my doubts without social anxiety of asking silly questions.
- (c) Emotion aware responses: the emotion and interaction driven feedback felt relatable and encouraged me to stay engaged and tailor the learning based on my liking.
- (d) Quiz based retention feedback: the quiz module after each subtopic, helped me analyze my progress and motivated me to work on my weak areas.
- (e) Personalized feedback loop: Personalized feedback after each subtopic learning session guided my learning choices and helped me reflect on content and strategy.

6 LIMITATIONS

Though Jignyasa provides a novel approach towards adaptive, emotionally aware, personalized learning, it still has limitations:

- 1. Emotional signals like facial expressions are processed by a public Vision language model. This can raised privacy concerns. In future, local VLMs and

LLMs should be integrated within ethical standards.

2. Currently user consent is explicitly taken for emotional data. But the system collects other data like interaction logs, tutor conversations. In future we will integrate multi-modal data. All the modalities must be included in a consent framework, abiding to governance policies.
3. Cloud based LLMs and VLMs currently used can introduce biases, data leaks.
4. A major aspect of education is peer to peer collaboration. Jignyasa currently lacks communication with other learners.
5. Jignyasa lacks real time adaptivity. Currently the personalization happens post subtopic session.
6. Jignyasa has undergone functional and self-reflective evaluation. It lacks large scale user testing. The finding cannot be generalized.

7 CONCLUSION

In the evolving landscape of life-long learning, current learning management systems do not offer emotionally intelligent and personalized education. This paper addresses the gap by designing and implementing Jignyasa- an AI powered, emotion-aware learning management system which integrates personalized learning paths, one-on-one tutoring and emotionally adaptive feedback mechanisms. The solution was designed and implemented with modular components like goal setting, personalized feedback, privacy based design and constructivism principles. Functional and self-reflective evaluation revealed Jignyasa's strengths and weaknesses. Quiz retention and dashboard component with personalized feedback enhanced engagement and learning. But the current implementation has limitations like usage of public cloud based language models used for analyzing learners personal data raising ethical concerns. The consent mechanism only focuses on emotional data and must incorporate other modalities. The lack of peer-to-peer interaction can affect social depth of learning. Jignyasa demonstrates the potential of achieving an affective, personalized and privacy based AI learning management system that can reshape learning and education. Future work will address the challenges mentioned as limitations and rigorous large scale user testing will ensure support of design for diverse learner groups. Jignyasa has the potential to revolutionize education and learning experiences.

8 FUTURE WORK

Based on current implementation and self-reflective insights, several future directions are planned:

1. To address privacy issues and improve performance, future versions of Jignyasa will integrate local LLMs and VLMs instead of cloud based AI models. This shift will support ethical AI standards.
2. The consent mechanism will be expanded to cover all the modalities which will ensure transparency and trust in learners.
3. New modules will be included to support peer to peer interaction aligning with social-constructivist educational theories.
4. Future iterations will explore affective computing models to enable deeper personalization.

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